

Where to install flow control gates in order to maximise in-sewer storage and reduce urban flood risk?

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Introduction

Pluvial flooding in urban areas has the potential to cause important damage to lives and property. Urban drainage managers, who design and operate drainage and infiltration infrastructure to mitigate urban flooding and sewer overflow, are often forced to make expensive, strategic decisions. However, in most drainage systems there might be a significant in-sewer volume that can be activated to store excess flow, attenuating peak flows and consequently mitigating the consequences of flooding with limited investment. This solution requires the installation of flow control gates (FCGs) along the system, which can maintain the flow in sewer system within desired bounds using relatively localised information. In this paper we present new methodologies to (a) estimate the potential in-sewer storage volume of a sewer system, (b) identify the best locations to install the flow control gates in order to maximise the in-sewer storage volume, and (c) compare volume of different return period rainfall events with the in-sewer system storage capacity.

Best locations for the flood control gates

To achieve objectives (i) and (ii) of this study, in a first step, we developed a new conversion tool in Java (Arnold *et al.*, 2000) to translate EPA Storm Water Management Model (SWMM) (Rossman, 2015) input (.inp) files into a spatial database, supported by PostGIS (Ramsey, 2005). This conversion tool is publicly available¹.

¹ <https://github.com/lidesousa/eawag.sww.centaur>

In our algorithm to calculate in-sewer storage volume and optimal gate location, we considered all manholes as potential locations for FCGs. We estimated the actual storage volume taking into account the cross-section and lengths of the pipes. To identify the most suitable locations for the FCGs. We proposed the following heuristics: (i) a maximum potential storage volume (Eq. 1), and (ii) a FCG location heuristic, which takes each network element volume and flow contributing areas into account (Eq. 2).

$$S = \sum_{i=1}^n V_i \quad (1)$$

$$S = A \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n V_i \quad (2)$$

Where S is the storage volume associated with the manhole, V is the volume, i is the pipes upstream the manhole and A is the impervious contributing area to the manhole.

Heuristic (i) computes the maximum storage volume of a gate located at a network node. It calculates and sums the pipe volume upstream the node until the lowest outflow height found (e.g., upstream manhole and weir); this process is similar to that presented by Philippon et al. (2015). Heuristic (ii), in addition to the volume evaluation, takes into account the total impervious area of the sub-catchments draining to each manhole, propagating the values to the downstream nodes where the flow originating from these sub-catchments will pass through. The inclusion of the contributing area in heuristic (ii) is explained by the fact that for large pipes (i.e., large storage) with small contributing areas the actual volume of water available to store can be small; so the inclusion of the contributing areas considers also the available water to store in the calculation leading to more realistic results.

Analysis of in-sewer storage capacity

The tool and the two heuristics were tested on a combined sewer system serving an urban catchment of approximately 90 ha in Lucerne (Switzerland), which comprises 333 pipes (over 11,000 m long) and 334 nodes. Figure 1 presents the drainage network with elevation information in the background. It is interesting to note that the upstream part of the catchment is steeper than the downstream part; this characteristic has an impact on the FCG location results.

Figure 1: Drainage network and elevation information in the background (grey, red and yellowish colours represent higher elevation values; green and blueish colours represent lower elevation values).

To analyse the storage potential of the catchment in Lucerne, different rainfall events with different intensities and fixed duration of 60 min were considered. To compare the rainfall intensities and volumes with the return periods of design rainfalls in Lucerne, the empirical equations developed by Hörler and Rhein (1962) were used.

Results

The results obtained using the location heuristics (i) and (ii) when applied to the case study network in Lucerne showed some differences between them; these are presented Table 1 and Figure 2.

Figure 2: Best locations to install the FCGs (red dots represent the results of Heuristic (i) while green dots represent the results of Heuristic (ii); the numbers represent the rank position; #1 represents the best place). The two heuristics swapped #1 and #2 positions

The differences are mainly due to the fact that with heuristic (ii) more information is taken into account: the contributing area. However, no definitive conclusions can be drawn yet from the differences obtained in these preliminary results. It would require further analyses including other drainage networks.

Table 1: Summary of the results obtained using the location heuristics (i) and (ii)

Number of gates	(i) Volume heuristic		(ii) Volume and area heuristic		Difference (%)	
	Cumulative storage volume (m ³)	Number of flooded manholes	Cumulative storage volume (m ³)	Number of flooded manholes	Storage volume (m ³)	Number of manholes
1	938	27	938	27	0	0
2	1,300	46	1,300	46	0	0
3	1,447	63	1,420	47	1.9	25.4
4	1,578	73	1,566	64	0.8	12.3
5	1,693	74	1,609	68	5.0	8.1

One first analysis showed that the maximum (theoretical) in-sewer storage capacity of the catchment used in this study is approximately 3,000 m³. It is a considerable large volume that may be activated with much smaller costs than with dedicated volume storage facilities, such as conventional stormwater tanks/reservoirs. However, when looking at the potential maximum storage volume at each location, one can see that the significant capacity is concentrated in a relatively small number of pipes.

When comparing the maximum in-sewer storage capacity and return period of rainfall events (Table 2), the in-sewer storage capacity represents approximately the volume of a 60 min duration one year return period event. To calculate the volume of the rainfall event (assumed with constant intensity and 60 min duration) we used a constant coefficient of 0.55 to represent the impervious characteristics of the catchment.

Table 2: Maximum in-sewer storage capacity and rainfall intensities

Intensity (mm h ⁻¹)	Duration (min)	Volume (m ³)	Comments
1	60	500	
2.5	60	1250	
5	60	2500	Less than Potential in-sewer storage capacity
7.5	60	3750	
10	60	5000	18 mm h⁻¹ is equivalent to a 60 min one year return period event
20	60	10000	
30	60	15000	

Conclusions

From our preliminary results we conclude that:the preliminary results shown herein, allow us to conclude that:

- In the specific case of the network analysed, there is a significant large in-sewer storage volume that can be used to store stormwater and hence reduce flow peaks and flood; this needs to be further investigated with other networks;
- Taking the volume and the contributing area into account leads to results that can be different from those obtained using only the network pipe volume. Adding the contributing area to the search heuristic brings important information regarding the hydrology response of the catchment decreasing the number of flooded manholes.

To incorporate the full dynamics of a combined sewer system into the optimal location of flow control gates, more detailed heuristics and algorithms should be explored.

Following the encouraging preliminary results presented in this paper, we are further developing the tool and heuristics in our public repository. The improvements being conducted are focused on: (a) the development of new heuristics to take into account

other factors, such as the number of sub-catchments and the variability of the sub-catchment characteristics ~~is also taken into account in the algorithm~~, and (b) the consideration of the most critical points (e.g., flooding areas) in the selection of the best location to install the gates.

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